

Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

**Adinda Putri Nur Aini, Lathifah Zaina Salsabilla, Eka Wahyu Hestya
Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi**

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis techniques by mapping research topics around the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) based on journals that have been collected. The research results show that there are 57 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES). The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES), both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES); Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

KHES (Compilation of Sharia Economic Law) was born after the publication of Law Number 3 of 2006, which was an amendment to Law Number 7 of 1989 concerning Religious Courts. In this way, the authority of the Religious Courts will broaden according to the development and needs of Muslims in Indonesia. Apart from having the authority to resolve marriage issues, wills, endowments, disputes, inheritance, grants and alms, the Religious Courts also handle requests such as adoptions, zakat disputes, ownership, infaq and other civil legal issues between fellow Muslims, including in the economic field sharia.

After KHES was issued by the Supreme Court, the public response to it was very positive, especially from people who were interested and involved in sharia economic law in Indonesia. KHES contributes to the unification and codification of sharia economic law in Indonesia.

Scientific journal publications about KHES continue to increase over time. According to the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garda), 40 journal documents have been published about KHES from 2006 to 2022. This shows that researchers discuss legal compilations more than applicable sharia laws.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Compilation of Sharia

Economic Law (KHES), so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES), both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

The Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) is an implementation of fiqh specifically for court heads. In the field of sharia economics, KHES is a reference for applied law used in Religious Courts. According to A. Djazuli, KHES is a compilation consisting of various legal sources, both from the sharia level as well as qanun (law) and fiqh. KHES can also be interpreted as a fatwa of Islamic law which has been adapted to current conditions in Indonesia. The Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) is a collection of norms or rules relating to sharia economic activities. KHES is the result of Indonesian jurisprudence thinking in the field of muamalat economics. KHES is one of the most important legal sources used by the chairman of the Religious Courts in Indonesia to examine activities related to sharia economics in Indonesia.

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can

be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Compilation of Sharia Economic Law ", "Compilation of Sharia Economic Law" and "KHES" for the entire year (20 05 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law

The results of searches for scientific publications regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law carried out during the period 2009 to 2022 show an increase and decrease in publications in several years, especially in the last two years. Of the 57 article titles obtained, 14 of them were published in 2021. The average publication of scientific articles regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law is more than five articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law by year

Year of Publication n	Number of Publication n Articles	Year of Publication n	Number of Publication n Articles	Year of Publication n	Number of Publication n Articles
2009	1	2016	4	2020	7
2012	1	2017	8	2021	14
2014	1	2018	4	2022	8
2015	5	2019	4		
Total 57					

Source 1: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows that there are seven affiliates or institutions that publish the most research articles regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law. El Thawalib Journal and Law Journal are the publishing institutions that publish the most research results regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law, namely seven articles each.

Table 2. Ranked 7th in institutions and journals publishing scientific publications regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Al-tsaman: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance	2
Istinbath	2
El-Thawalib Journal	7
Journal of Legal Ideas	2
Law Journal	7
Law Journal of the Legal Science Study Program, Faculty of Law, Untan (S1 Student Journal, Faculty of Law) Tanjungpura University	2
ISLAMIC JOURNAL	2

Source 2: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that the most productive researchers are Muhammad Azani Nasution from Lancang Kuning University, Hasan Basri from Lancang Kuning University, Dewi Nurjannah from Lancang Kuning University, and Nurhadi from STAI Al-Azhar Pekanbaru Riau Indonesia, each of whom wrote six articles.

Table 3. Researcher productivity around the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law

Researcher	Number of Publications
Muhammad Azani Nasution (Lancang Kuning University), Hasan Basri (Lancang Kuning University), Dewi Nurjannah (Lancang Kuning University)	3
Nurhadi (STAI Al-Azhar Pekanbaru Riau Indonesia)	3
Muhammad Syahrullah (Muhammadiyah University of Riau)	2
(Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Emiliani et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Zahro et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rahmawati et al., 2023) (Shalsabila et al., 2023) (Fitriawati et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Febrian & Budianto, 2023) (Rohmah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023)	

Source 3Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law

Search results for research articles on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, captured and analyzed using VOSView er. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 5. Color consists of 10 topics, namely: comparison, compilation, contract, etc., fatwas, ijarah, rule, sharia economic law, transaction, weakness.
- Cluster 6. Color consists of 7 topics, namely concept, grant, Islamic economic law, khi, purchase, purchase agreement, terms.

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Research around the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES)

Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 57 Research topics surrounding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES), namely:

1. AKAD BAY', IJARAH AND WADI'AH PERSPECTIVE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW (KHES)
2. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE PRINCIPLE OF FREEDOM OF CONTRACT IN BUYING AND SELLING ACCORDING TO THE CIVIL LAW BOOK AND THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW
3. CLAUSES IN THE STANDARD LAUNDRY SERVICES CONTRACT (According to Law Number 8 of 1999 concerning Consumer Protection and Compilation of Sharia Economic Law)
4. Contracts in the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) and Their Implementation in a Warung
5. TYPOLOGY OF GUARANTEES: A COMPILATION PERSPECTIVE OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW AND CIVIL GUARANTEES
6. STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PERMA NUMBER 2 OF 2008 CONCERNING THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW (KHES) AS A GUIDELINE FOR SETTLEMENT OF SHARIA ECONOMIC CASES IN THE RELIGIOUS COURTS
7. Compilation of Sharia Economic Law: General Overview of Islamic Law
8. CONSTRUCTION OF CONTEMPORARY ISLAMIC ECONOMIC LAW (ANALYSIS OF "JASSER AUDA SYSTEM THEORY" ON THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW)
9. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SALE AND PURCHASE AGREEMENTS ACCORDING TO THE CIVIL LAW BOOK AND COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW
10. Weaknesses of Fatwa and Compilation of Sharia Economic Law in Economic Legislation Policy in Indonesia
11. BUILDING AN ISLAMIC LEGAL PARADIGM FOR RENEWING SHARIA BUSINESS LAW IN INDONESIA: ANALYTICAL STUDY ON A COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW
12. ISLAMIC LEGAL PHILOSOPHY AGREEMENT COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW
13. THE IMPLEMENTATION OF KHIYAR TERMS IN BUYING AND BUYING AT THE SANGKUMPAL BONANG PADANGSI MARKET IS REVIEWED FROM A COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW
14. Building an Islamic Legal Paradigm for Renewing Sharia Business Law in Indonesia: An Analytical Study on the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law
15. Concept of Legal Subjects in Islamic Law, Positive Law and Compilation of Sharia Economic Law
16. Management of Public Economic Sectors in the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law

17. THE CONCEPT OF MURĀBAHAH IN THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN RELIGIOUS JURISDICTION
18. Transfer of Rights to the Object of the Ijarah Muntahiyah bi Tamlik Agreement with Wa`ad (Promise) of Grant in the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law
19. The Existence of a Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) as a Guide for Judges in Resolving Sharia Economic Cases in Religious Courts
20. FORMALIZATION OF THE RAHN AGREEMENT IN THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW
21. IMPLEMENTATION OF RAHN AGREEMENTS IN SHARIA Pawnshops BASED ON A COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAWS IN PEKANBARU
22. Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) in a General Review of Islamic Law
23. Internalization of Islamic Business Ethics Values in the Compilation Perspective of Sharia Economic Law
24. Consequence Analysis of the Weaknesses of the Contract Concept in the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law
25. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE PRINCIPLES OF SALE AND PURCHASE AGREEMENTS ACCORDING TO A COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW AND THE CIVIL LAW BOOK
26. Increasing Public Understanding of Lease Agreements (Ijarah) Based on the Compilation of Sharia Economic Laws (KHES) for the Community of Kerinci Kanan District, Siak Regency
27. History and Position of the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law in Supreme Court Regulation Number 2 of 2008 in Indonesia
28. COMPILATION ANALYSIS OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW ON MUAMALAH PRACTICES IN PURCHASING MANGO FRUITS USING THE TEAS SYSTEM
29. Partelon Profit Sharing System for Rice Farmers in Palengaan, Pamekasan Regency, Perspective of Islamic Law and Compilation of Sharia Economic Law
30. SHARIA CARD LEGISLATION: IMPLEMENTATION IN THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAWS AND FATWAS OF THE NATIONAL SHARIA COUNCIL OF THE INDONESIAN ULAMA COUNCIL
31. IMPLEMENTATION OF SALE AND PURCHASE AGREEMENT TRANSACTIONS IN THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW (KHES) TAMPAN PEKANBARU DISTRICT
32. Community Empowerment in Understanding Kafalah Contracts Based on the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) in Pandau Jaya Village, Siak Hulu District
33. Rubber Farming Management Viewed from the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law
34. Lifetime Guarantee on Tupperware Products in Jember Perspective of Sharia Economic Law Compilation
35. Aqad Syirkah: In a Compilation of Sharia Economic Law and the Maliki School
36. Increasing Public Understanding of Motor Vehicle Credit Sale and Purchase Transactions Based on the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES) in Sialangmunggu Village, Tuah Madani District, Pekanbaru City

37. PAYMENT OBJECTS IN THE CIVIL LAW BOOK AND THE COMPILATION OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW: A Comparative Review
38. Islamic Economics in the Indonesian Economic System (Study of the Principles of Islamic Economics in KHES and Their Implementation in the National Economy)
39. SYNERGY OR CONFLICT OF LAWS? (COMPARISON BETWEEN THE COMPILATION OF RULES ON SHARIAH ECONOMY (KHES) AND THE NATIONAL SHARIAH BOARD'S (DSN) FATWAS)
40. Accounting in Maqashid Syariah Perspective; KHES analysis with Masalahah Najmuddin ath-Thufi
41. Sharia Economic Disputes: Study of Judge's Decision No.0459/Pdt.G/2016/PA.Sby in the KHES Perspective
42. FIKIH, KHI AND KHES PERSPECTIVE GRANT
43. Fiqh Rational about Zakat and In Grants Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES)
44. Gashb and Itlaf Arrangements in KHES and Authority of Justice (Review of Chapter XV of Book II of KHES)
45. TRANSFER OF LAND RENTAL RIGHTS IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF MU'AMALAH FIQIH, Civil Code AND KHES
46. Implementation of Sand Buying and Selling in the KHES Study
47. MURABAHAH FINANCING IN THE SELLING AND BUYING TRANSACTION SYSTEM ACCORDING TO THE FATWA DSN MUI AND KHES, OR THE VAT LAW
48. Buying and Selling Vegetables Reviewed by KHES
49. Mattress Making Reviewed by KHES
50. Utilization of Palm Oil Land Pawning viewed from KHES
51. Wadiah Concept According to Fiqh and KHES
52. Interpretation of Contracts and Dispute Resolution in Engagement Law Perspective of Muammalah Kulliyah's Fiqh Principles (Comparative Study of KHES and Civil Code)
53. Transportation Services Reviewed by KHES
54. Ownership Rights of Stitching Remains Reviewed by KHES
55. The Codification of Sharia Norms in The Compilation of Sharia Economic Law
56. EXISTENCE OF KHIYAR IN ONLINE TRANSACTIONS (E COMMERCE) (COMPILATION OF SHARIAH ECONOMIC LAW)
57. ISSUE OF GRANT PROPERTY WITHDRAWAL IN ARTICLE 712 OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW COMPILATION AND ARTICLE 212 OF ISLAMIC LAW COMPILATION

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 57 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding the Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES).

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